

Screening for Diabetes by Indian Diabetic Risk Score (IDRS) and Awareness about Oral and Systemic Complications of Diabetes in a Rural Community of Central India

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Abstract

Background- Diabetes is one of the top ten causes of death worldwide and one of the biggest health emergencies of the twenty-first century. Globally, 463 million people have diabetes in 2019, with a 51% increase expected by 2045, when 700 million people would be impacted by diabetes. Among non-communicable diseases, diabetes is the most prevalent in India. Diabetes is a growing challenge in India and is now '*Diabetic Capital of the World*'.

Aim & Objective - The aim of the study was to assess the prevalence of diabetes and associated risk factors by screening for Diabetes by Indian Diabetic Risk Score (IDRS) and to create awareness about oral and systemic complications of diabetes and to educate people about prevention and treatment of diabetes in a Rural Community of Central India.

Methods and Materials – The cross sectional community based study was conducted in rural area of Nagpur district, Maharashtra, India. Awareness about diabetes oral and systemic complications and its prevention was discussed with the rural population through PowerPoint presentation and posters. The Sample size was 1500 participants including both genders. Four parameters like participant's family history, Age, Physical activity and waist circumference was noted and score was given as per IDRS scoring system on a pre formed proforma.

Result- Among 870 Males, 186 are under high risk (22%), 525 (60%) under medium risk and 159 (18%) under low risk category. Among female out of 630 participants, 226 (36%) are high risk, 302 (48%) are medium risk and 102 (16%) are low risk category. Among both genders, 412 (28%) participants are at high risk, 827 (55%) at medium risk and 261 (17%) at low risk.

Conclusion:-Diabetes is increasingly growing in rural regions due to a lack of understanding. Raising awareness about Diabetes Mellitus and its oral and systemic consequences is crucial in Rural India with this simple screening tool.

KEY WORDS: Indian Diabetic Risk Score; Screening; Diabetes; Risk factors; Rural community, Diabetes Awareness

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is known as the '*silent killer*' since its subtle symptoms which are often missed and increased blood sugar level acts as a '*poison*'. Among non-communicable diseases, diabetes is most prevalent in India. Diabetes is one of the top ten causes of death worldwide and one of the biggest health emergencies of the twenty-first century. India's diabetes population is expanding at an extremely fast rate. The primary causes of this shift have been Indians longer lifespans and propensity for developing diabetes mellitus at an earlier age [1]. Recently it was

observed in a study conducted by Indian Council of Medical Research that Diabetes is a growing challenge in India and is now '*Diabetic Capital of the World*' [2].

As per the World Health Organization, "*Diabetes is a chronic, metabolic disease characterized by elevated levels of blood glucose (or blood sugar), which leads over time to serious damage to the heart, blood vessels, eyes, kidneys and nerves.*" The prevalence of Type 2 Diabetes is most commonly occurred in adults when body becomes resistant to produce required amount of insulin. Type 2 diabetes has increased substantially in countries of all income levels over the last three decades. Non-communicable diseases accounted for 74% of all fatalities worldwide in 2019; diabetes was the primary cause of 1.6 million of these deaths. It was estimated that 592 million deaths worldwide would result from diabetes by 2035 [3].

According to *Current Global Statistics*, 463 million people have diabetes in 2019, with a 51% increase expected by 2045, when 700 million people would be impacted by diabetes. By 2025, there will be a global agreement to restrict the increase number of new cases of diabetes and obesity. Access to affordable medication, particularly insulin, is crucial for those living with diabetes. Diabetes affects around 422 million people globally, with the majority residing in low- and middle-income countries, and diabetes is directly responsible for 1.5 million fatalities per year. Diabetes has been progressively increasing in both the number of cases and the prevalence during the last few decades [4].

According to the 10th edition of the *International Diabetes Federation (IDF) Diabetes Atlas*, the prevalence of diabetes is continuing to rise globally, indicating that diabetes poses a serious threat to people's health and well-being as well as that of their families and communities. One in ten adults, or 537 million, have diabetes between 20–79 age groups. By 2030 and 2045, this number is expected to increase to 643 million and 783 million, respectively [5].

More than three-quarters of adult diabetics reside in low and middle income nations. Diabetes will be the cause of 6.7 million fatalities, or one every five seconds. Diabetes has resulted in health expenditures of at least USD 966 billion, representing a 316% increase over the previous 15 years. Impaired Glucose Tolerance (IGT) puts 541 million persons at high risk of developing type 2 diabetes. Currently, 8.8% of the adult population have diabetes out of which 9.6% were men and 9.0% were women [6].

In *Southeast Asia*, diabetes affects 1 out of every 11 adults which estimates as 90 million. Diabetes is estimated to affect 113 million adults by 2030 and 151 million by 2045. Over one-half of all adults with diabetes are undiagnosed. 747,000 fatalities in 2021 just because of diabetes. 10 billion USD was the Expenditure for this issue in 2021. By 2045, 152 million adults in South East Asia are expected to have diabetes, a 68% increase from the current figure [7-8].

A survey of 160 WHO member states revealed that approximately 60% have conducted national surveys of blood glucose concentrations, 50% have a diabetes registry, and 80% have an action plan in place [9]. Ultimately, effective testing, diagnosis, treatment, and diabetes control are lacking, particularly in LMICs [10]. As our forecasts suggest that nearly 50% of the increases in diabetes prevalence will be due to changing demographic profiles, countries will need to invest in health systems to handle the surge in expected patients [11].

The prevalence of diabetes in *India* has risen from 7.1% in 2009 to 8.9% in 2019. It is also estimated that nearly 57% of adults with diabetes are undiagnosed in India, which is approximately 43.9 million. Recent surveys indicate that diabetes now affects 5-8% of rural population in India giving the impression of the epidemic to be transpiring in the rural areas [12].

A higher risk of all-cause death was linked to the fact that, regrettably, over half of India's diabetics are still ignorant that they have the condition. Inappropriate treatment and a delayed diagnosis lead to a worst prognosis [13]. Realizing how critical it is to quickly spread the diabetes pandemic to India's rural population, which makes up around 70% of the country's population [14].

A community health worker can filter out high-risk individuals using a very simplified measure, the '*Indian Diabetes Risk Score*' (IDRS). This score is based on multiple logistic regression analysis derived from the '*Chennai Urban Rural Epidemiology Study*' (CURES), which is the largest population-based study of diabetes in

India. IDRS's affordability and ease of use make it a great option for mass screening initiatives. Two modifiable risk variables, waist circumference and physical inactivity and two non-modifiable risk factors, age and family history of diabetes are used by IDRS to describe the possibility of significantly lowering the risk score by improving the modifiable risk factors. Subjects having moderate IDRS are excellent candidates for lifestyle adjustment regardless of their blood sugar status since they are at risk for both diabetes and cardiovascular disease [15].

Therefore, early detection of those with undiagnosed diabetes mellitus and those at risk of getting the disease in the near future is crucial for preventing morbidity associated with diabetic complications and decreasing the financial burden. This emphasizes the value of screening programs in identifying those at high risk of diabetes early, when simple lifestyle modifications might help to delay or avoid the beginning of the condition.

The theme for 'World Health Day-2016' has been aptly selected to be '*Beat Diabetes*'. World Health Organization (WHO) Launched the first Global report on diabetes, which describe the burden and consequences of diabetes and advocate for stronger health systems to ensure improved surveillance, enhanced prevention, and more effective management of diabetes".

This study was done to partly contribute in WHO campaign to identify high risk cases of diabetes in rural community using *Indian Diabetes Risk Score* (IDRS). The aim of the study was to assess the prevalence of diabetes and associated risk factors by screening for Diabetes by Indian Diabetic Risk Score(IDRS) and to create awareness about oral and systemic complications of diabetes and to educate people about prevention and treatment of diabetes in a Rural Community of Central India.

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

Study design, study settings and ethics

A descriptive cross-sectional community-based study was conducted in three villages in the Nagpur district. Institutional Ethics Committee (VSPM'S DCRC/Dean/IEC/10/2016 Dated 02/09/2016) approval was obtained. Maharashtra University of Health Sciences, Nashik, Maharashtra, India, has approved a *Short-Term Research Funding* for this project for the 2017–18 academic session.

Sample size

The total population of small village was approximately 1500 living in approximately 250 houses. In each house, the mean number of adults above the age of 20 years was two, which gives a total number of adult populations of approximately 500 in one village. So, the total population of three rural areas was approximately 1500 [16].

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Participants including both males and females with age more than 20 years and willing to participate and exclude known cases of type -1 Diabetes Mellitus, Pregnant women and unwilling subjects.

Research Instrument

'*Indian Diabetes Risk Score*' (IDRS) Screening tool was used to collect the data. The IDRS was created by Mohan et al. and includes two modifiable risk factors for diabetes (waist circumference, physical activity) and two non-modifiable risk factors (age, family history). The dependent variable in the multiple logistic regression study, which used undiagnosed diabetes, was the beta coefficient. The best results for identifying undiagnosed diabetes were obtained with an IDRS value $>$ or $=$ 60, which also had the best sensitivity (72.5%), specificity (60.1%), positive predictive value (17.0%), negative predictive value (95.1%), and accuracy (61.3%) [15].

Data collection and Statistical analysis

After taking informed consent from the participants, Family history, physical activity details noted and waist circumference was measured. After data collection as per IDRS the values entered in excel sheet and statistical analysis was done. After combining all indicators, a score more than 60 indicates a High risk, between 30-50 considered Moderate risk and less than 30 as Low risk as per Table 1. After screening, those patients who were at

high risk and medium risk were referred to the Hospital for blood glucose test and medications were prescribed by the medical Professionals.

Table 1: IDRS consisting of following details with scores derived from CURES [15]-

Type of Risk Factors	Risk factors	Particulars	Score
Non-Modifiable Risk Factors	Age	<35 years	0
		35-49 years	20
		>50 years	30
	Family history	No family history of diabetes	0
Either parent's diabetic		10	
Both parent's diabetic		20	
Modifiable Risk Factors	Abdominal obesity	Waist <80 cm (female), <90 cm (male)	0
		Waist 80-89 cm (female), 90-99 cm (male)	10
		Waist >90 cm (female) >100 cm (male)	20
		Physical activity	0
	Vigorous exercise and strenuous labor at home/work	Mild exercise at home/work	10
		moderate exercise at home/work	20
No exercise or sedentary lifestyle at home/work		30	
Total Score		Minimum Score	0
		Maximum score	100

Awareness campaign

Awareness about diabetes signs, symptoms, oral complications (tooth decay, periodontal diseases, xerostomia, tooth sensitivity, halitosis, salivary gland dysfunction) and systemic complications (diabetic neuropathy, diabetic retinopathy, diabetic nephropathy and heart diseases and sexual dysfunction) and its prevention was discussed with the rural population through-Power point presentation and posters. Pamphlets about healthy lifestyle, diet, and exercise to prevent diabetes were distributed to all participants. They learned how to prevent diabetes by managing their weight, eating a healthy, well-balanced diet, exercising frequently, getting regular check-ups, regularly checking their feet for cuts and blisters, and quitting smoking.

III. RESULTS

Total 1500 participants including both male ($n=870$) and female ($n=630$) participated in this study.

Table 2 shows, among males out of 870 participants, 186 are under high risk category which is 22%, medium risk category there are 525 participants which is 60%, low risk category there are 159 participants which is 18%. Among female out of 630 subjects 226 are high risk which is 36%, 302 are medium risk category which is 48%, 102 are low risk category which is 16% of total subjects.

Table-2-According to the gender distribution participants at Risk for Diabetes Mellitus

Sex	High	Medium	Low	Total
Male	186 (22%)	525 (60%)	159 (18%)	870
Female	226 (36%)	302 (48%)	102 (16%)	630
Total	412	827	261	1500

Table 3 shows, 412 (28%) participants are at high risk, 827 (55%) are at medium risk and 261 (17%) are at low risk of both genders as per the IDRS.

Table-3- Total Number of Population at Risk as per IDRS Scores (Category-High, Medium and Low Risk)

Category	No of participants (Both Male/Female)	Percentage
High (Risk score >60)	412	28%
Medium (Risk score 30-50)	827	55%
Low(Risk score <30)	261	17%
Total	1500	100%

IV. DISCUSSION

A population screening tool, the Indian diabetes risk score, was employed to detect high-risk individuals living in rural areas. Research conducted throughout India has reported prevalence rates ranging from 13% to 25%.

An investigation by Chaitali Ashutosh Gore *et al.*, 314 people were involved in the study. There were 164 (52.2%) females and 150 (47.8%) males. A high risk IDRS of 60 or more was recorded in 220 (70.1%), a moderate risk IDRS of 30 to 50 in 83 (26.4%), and a low risk IDRS of <30 in only 11 (3.5%) of participants, compared to the study's low, moderate, and high risk categories of 17%, 55%, and 28%, respectively [17].

Data from 155 individuals in a study by Puja Dudeja *et al.* were analyzed. 41 cases of previously undiagnosed diabetes were confirmed; 39 (97%) of these cases had IDRS scores of greater than 60, and none of them had a score lower than 30 [18].

In a study conducted by Mongjam Meghachandra Singh *et al.*, 290 medical students participated. In contrast to the 17%, 55%, and 28% in the low, moderate, and high-risk categories observed in this study, the IDRS categorization revealed 77%, 22%, and 1% of pupils in these categories [19].

In another study by Tarun Bhatia *et al.*, out of 222 students who underwent screening using the Indian Diabetes Risk Score, roughly 1% were classified as high risk, 68% as moderate risk, and roughly 31% as low risk. In contrast, the results of this study showed that the low, moderate, and high risk categories were, respectively, 17%, 55%, and 28% [20].

V. CONCLUSION

In rural areas, the prevalence of diabetes is rising quickly. Increasing public awareness of diabetes mellitus and its complications is imperative. It puts more stress on India's rural health systems, which are already in dire straits. In order to mitigate the morbidity and mortality linked to diabetes, basic diagnostic instruments that can recognize high-risk individuals at the outset of interactions with healthcare providers are necessary. The Indian diabetes risk score has been shown to be effective in this study in identifying high-risk diabetic subjects in the community. Diabetes mellitus cases can be diagnosed using the risk categories, which can also be used to raise important awareness about the control of modifiable risk factors for the disease.

Strength and Limitation

IDRS is a highly cost-effective population-based diabetes screening strategy that can be implemented in India. Better results will undoubtedly come from early diabetes detection using IDRS as a simplest screening tool, which also helps to lower the incidence and negative effects of diabetes. World Diabetes Day, observed on November 14 worldwide, offers a chance to increase awareness of diabetes as a global public health concern and the steps

that must be taken, both individually and collectively, to improve the condition's diagnosis, treatment, and prevention.

This study did not include blood glucose level measurements to compare with the Indian Diabetic Risk Score (IDRS); additionally, due to participants' lack of awareness about diabetes mellitus, the family history provided by participants cannot be relied on. More people could have been tested for Diabetes Mellitus, but due to time constraints, this was not possible.

Future Recommendations

Prospective follow-up is necessary to evaluate the predictive power of the Indian Diabetic Risk Score (IDRS) in non-diabetic subjects with high risk scores. Participants should be taught about lifestyle modification to lower the risk to their precious life. Risk factors, such as waist circumference and physical activity, can be altered which leads to a reduction in risk level. To compare the risk score among participants, the study can be conducted in both rural and urban areas.

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